

NAVIGATING TRANSITIONS: SUSTAINING COMMUNITY COLLABORATIONS IN DIGITAL PRESERVATION

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Abstract – Community-driven endeavors play a critical role in digital preservation by fostering collaboration, knowledge exchange, and shared infrastructure. However, many community-based programs in the United States operate with limited

resources and volunteer labor, making sustainability and governance transitions challenging. This paper will showcase five digital preservation initiatives—NDSA, BitCurator Consortium, Software Preservation Network, Digital Preservation Coalition, and ePADD—

to discuss their recent transitions, lessons learned, and strategies for building long-term capacity. By aligning with the iPres 2025 theme, "Tūhono (Connect)," this paper will explore the vital role of community, collaboration, and capacity-building in ensuring the future of digital preservation networks.

Keywords - Community, collaboration, people

I. INTRODUCTION

Community collaborations in the United States serve as essential networks in digital preservation, facilitating knowledge-sharing, advocacy, and resource development. Many of these organizations rely heavily on volunteer labor, which can create challenges in sustaining long-term efforts, securing funding, and transitioning leadership or administrative hosts. This paper will explore how five key organizations are navigating similar critical transitions, from changing administrative hosts to hiring dedicated staff and securing financial sustainability. By examining these cases, we aim to provide insights and strategies for strengthening community-driven digital preservation efforts.

II. BITCURATOR CONSORTIUM

The BitCurator Consortium was founded in 2014 to serve as the host and center of administrative, user, and community support for the BitCurator Environment. The BitCurator Consortium (BCC) promotes the development of innovative, sustainable curation of born-digital materials by any organization responsible for caring for such materials. Our organizational vision is to address the articulated needs of the BCC community—training, collaboration, research, software development, documentation, integration, scripts—while advocating for the expansion of digital forensics practice worldwide.

In February 2024 Educopia announced new hosting criteria for member communities starting January 2025: 1 Full Time Equivalent (FTE) and a healthy operational reserve. After sharing and reviewing a variety of community financial projections from 2024 through 2028, BCC leadership and Educopia met, and BCC leadership determined working together to find BCC a new fiscal host would best serve its membership. This decision was informed by a combination of factors:

- Raising membership fees in the 2024 calendar year was perceived as too risky - it could take a full quarter or more to prepare the community for an informed vote on new membership tiers. The resulting decision could mean the loss of members and a major reduction in revenue.
- Since the current operational reserve is still below the target operational reserve in the Operational Reserve Policy, the loss of member revenue could lead to a shorter timeline for finding an alternative host, merging with another community, or sunsetting -- which would be much more disruptive for community members.

The goal was to work in partnership with Educopia through 2024 for a transition that served the BCC and the BitCurator Environment. BCC Executive Council and Educopia partnered on a goal of researching and identifying a new fiscal host for the BCC. We determined an accelerated timeline for the move that would start January 2025.

In order to work towards this goal we established a temporary committee dubbed the Transition Team. The Transition Team was tasked with determining the best fit for a new fiscal host. The team was made up of the three Executive members who were entering their second term, Educopia staff, and a BCC member. Starting in May 2024, the Transition Team held one hour weekly meetings. Throughout the summer the team worked together to build a program dossier, a software environment dossier, learn about different fiscal sponsorship models, and establish a list of potential sponsors to reach out to. Members of the Transition Team contacted five fiscal sponsors and interviewed four. After all of our interviews, research, and careful consideration of the fiscal sponsors the Transition Team agreed to apply to two hosts. The Transition Team submitted applications to both sponsors in August 2024. In November 2024 the community voted to approve the Open Library Foundation as the new fiscal sponsor for the BCC. The planning of the move of assets, materials, finances of the BCC began in December 2024 with a target completion date of April 1, 2025.

The Transition Team felt it was important to keep the community informed. The majority of the 2024 monthly community calls were focused on

updates related to the transition. We also posted public communications about the transition to our website as a way to communicate with external stakeholders the status of the BCC.

Throughout our search for a new fiscal host, the Transition Team gained a deeper understanding of fiscal sponsorship. First, we had to familiarize ourselves with different sponsorship models used in the United States. Many organizations, such as Educopia, offer comprehensive fiscal sponsorship (Model A), where the fiscal sponsor assumes all legal and financial liability of the project. In Model L, the fiscal sponsor serves as the sole owner of a charitable LLC, with the project operating as a single-member LLC (SMLLC). The fiscal sponsor is shielded from liabilities and the project can receive donations in its own name. In both Models A and L, the project is treated as a part of the sponsor when filing taxes. In joining the Open Library Foundation, which uses Model L, the BCC became an SMLLC.

The Transition Team also learned about the implications of different staffing structures of potential fiscal sponsors. While BCC was under Educopia, the latter provided 0.5 Full Time Equivalent (FTE) staffing for community facilitation. More staff and contractor hours were billed for event, website, and communications support as needed. The new fiscal sponsors BCC considered offer different levels and types of staffing to their projects. While the Open Library Foundation includes accounting, legal, and website support in its fiscal hosting fee, the organization is volunteer-run and does not have full-time staff who can provide extra support to projects. Thus, the BCC hired a part-time contractor for administrative support.

As the Transition Team navigated the process of changing fiscal hosts, several takeaways emerged. Before identifying potential fiscal sponsors, it is essential to have clarity around your organization's unique value proposition and the specific needs of your community. Before the transition, the BCC held town halls and administered a community survey. The Transition Team also held discussions to identify the core needs from a fiscal sponsor and staff, e.g. bookkeeping, administrative, and software maintenance support.

While there are fiscal sponsors focused on libraries and cultural heritage organizations, it can be

helpful to consider those beyond that domain. For example, the Transition Team also spoke with fiscal sponsors who support software and technology projects. When meeting with a sponsor, both organizations are interviewing each other, and it is important to assess whether there is an alignment in vision and values. The application process may differ depending on the organization. However, a community seeking a new fiscal sponsor should also be prepared to address the following in their application: financial sustainability, governance structure, and assets and intellectual property.

III. DIGITAL PRESERVATION COALITION (DPC)

The Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) builds and sustains a welcoming and inclusive global community that works together to bring about a sustainable future for our digital assets. The DPC is a membership organization that is managed by a team of full-time staff and overseen by a Board of Directors appointed from our Full Members. Most of our income is derived from annual subscription fees paid by members.

In 2002, the DPC was established as a collaboration between multiple agencies operating in the UK and Ireland. In 2014, the DPC opened its membership to the whole world and since then has seen the membership diversify both in terms of geography and organization type. One of the challenges of this growth and diversification has been ensuring that all members are able to access the benefits of DPC membership equitably, regardless of their geography.

Therefore, in 2019, an internationalization objective was added to our mandate and in 2020, an office in Melbourne was established and an Australia-based DPC member of staff was added to the team. These actions were taken to ensure that our growing membership in Australasia could benefit from dedicated support and a program in a proximate time zone.

In 2022, the DPC adopted a new Strategic Plan committing the Coalition to 'create, empower, structure and extend a global community, working together for a sustainable digital legacy'. Following

the model established in Australasia, between 2022-2024 a small group of DPC members united as the DPC Americas Task Force, which reported to the Executive Board, to guide and support the planning of the establishment of a DPC presence in the Americas. This group ensured accountability to the Executive Board, visibility to all DPC members, and engagement with stakeholders. This Taskforce has transitioned to be a part of a larger Stakeholder Group and continues to guide the development of the DPC Americas Program to ensure it delivers substantial benefits and value for members in the region.

The DPC Americas program launched in 2024 and gained a full-time staff member in June 2024 (Anna Perricci). With support of the full DPC team, members in the Americas can access member benefits on an equal footing with members in other parts of the world (e.g. via events in more convenient timeframes and locations).

In addition, establishing an additional presence in the Americas and Australasia means that DPC members around the world now have a solid network through which to exchange, learn from and amplify the digital preservation work which is taking place across the globe. Though most meetings and webinars are conducted virtually, a small number of gatherings for on-site networking and information sharing are held annually on three continents..

The DPC's capacity to understand and respond to the institutional contexts of digital preservation around the world is quickly expanding. As of April 2025, the DPC is now active in 25 countries with over 175 members, including 26 members across Australasia and Asia-Pacific and 31 member organizations located in the Americas. A little under half of our members are based in the UK and a bit over half of our members are located throughout the rest of the world.

The lessons learned through the planning and launch processes for both regions include that it can take several years to shape and advance a program tasked with serving stakeholders in new

regions. We rely on our members for guidance on everything we do, from our annual work plans to how to meet various needs across the world. Each of the 14 members of staff at the DPC have a critical role to play in the implementation of member-driven plans, including providing equitable access to DPC resources. Though there is only one staff member physically located in the Americas, the program's success is truly the combined accomplishment of the DPC's staff, member-leaders and stakeholders.

IV. ePADD

ePADD is free and open source software, originally developed by Stanford University Libraries, that supports the appraisal, processing, preservation, discovery, and delivery of email archives. ePADD has pioneered the application of machine learning and natural language processing to confront challenges that collection stakeholders routinely face in stewarding email collections of historical value. This includes screening email for confidential, or legally-protected information, preparing email for preservation, and making email archives discoverable to researchers.

Initial work on ePADD began in 2010, and over the years, the project has received funding from the National Historical Publications & Records Commission (2012-2015), the Institute of Museum and Library Services (2015-2018), the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation (2020-2021), and the Email Archiving : Building Capacity and Community (EA-BCC) grant program, administered by the University of Illinois (2021-2022). The EA-BCC grant-funded project marked an intentional expansion in community governance of ePADD, with Harvard Library and the University of Manchester Libraries joining Stanford in strategic development. Although the project has been sustained by a grant funded model, the team understood the need to transition to a more sustainable funding and governance model to ensure that ePADD would continue to serve its large, international user base. In 2023, the ePADD Steering Group and ePADD Code Group were launched — two volunteer groups focused on formalizing ePADD's governance and expanding the base of code contributors respectively.

The Steering and Code Groups are exploring the potential to partner with an organizational host

to manage aspects of the project. To this end, the Steering Group outlined the ongoing organizational and technical requirements for maintaining the software, interviewed potential organizational hosts that focus on open source software projects in the library and archives space, and consulted with peer projects about their sustainability strategies. Those discussions have given the Steering Group a better picture of the support and services offered by potential organizational hosts.

Equally important in this process has been engaging with and providing transparency to the ePADD user community. The focus of a 2024 community meeting was bringing visibility to the labor and fiscal investments required to maintain a stable codebase while balancing legitimate concerns about potentially incurring user costs in a transition to a host. These open discussions have equipped the Steering Group with a more precise benchmark of project and community needs, as they continue evaluating options.

V. NDSA

NDSA (formerly the National Digital Stewardship Alliance) is a consortium of 278 partnering organizations [1], including universities, professional associations, businesses, government agencies, and nonprofit organizations, all committed to the long-term preservation of digital information. NDSA has been an organizing force for the preservation community for more than fifteen years, bringing together a global network of collaborative partners to drive activities related to the long-term preservation of digital information.

Since its founding in 2010, NDSA has relied on financial and logistical support from host institutions, first the Library of Congress and later the Council on Library and Information Resources (CLIR). CLIR has been a key partner in NDSA's development, and NDSA has valued their support over the years. However, shifting organizational priorities and leadership changes at CLIR gradually reshaped this arrangement. When NDSA began with CLIR in 2016, CLIR had not yet developed its Affiliates program, through which it provides integrated fiscal and administrative services for a fee. NDSA was effectively grandfathered into the Affiliates program despite never being able to contribute financially back to CLIR under this fiscal hosting model.

Over the years NDSA has grown significantly, expanding its programs, membership, and impact. In 2023, NDSA leadership began actively exploring new hosting options, recognizing the need for a long-term sustainability plan. As part of this process, NDSA conducted member surveys, interviews, and listening sessions, revealing a strong demand for a dedicated digital preservation community. Members highly value existing resources like the Levels of Digital Preservation but seek greater opportunities for collaboration and knowledge-sharing. Professional development remains a top priority, with strong interest in expanded training, roundtables, and peer-to-peer problem-solving. Many members join NDSA not only for continued learning but also to demonstrate their institution's commitment to digital preservation and contribute to the field. Members also emphasized the need for more advocacy tools and resources. There was also strong interest in regional events as a more affordable way to foster in-person engagement, hands-on learning, and local networking—particularly for smaller institutions.

This assessment underscores the need for sustained investment in community-building, education, improved onboarding, and cost-accessible participation models. However, effectively coordinating these activities requires dedicated administrative support. NDSA hopes to fund and hire a program manager to provide the necessary oversight, ensuring that these initiatives are strategically developed, efficiently executed, and continuously assessed for impact. This role will manage logistical planning, communications, and outreach while also supporting member engagement and feedback mechanisms, improving NDSA's ability to serve the digital preservation community effectively. To support these efforts, NDSA is actively fundraising and has applied for a grant from the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS). However, the future of IMLS funding remains uncertain, highlighting the need for a diversified and sustainable financial model.

Identifying a new host has been a challenging, multi-year process. After conducting an analysis of its needs from a host organization, NDSA sought expressions of interest from potential hosts last year [2]. As NDSA transitions to a new host and seeks to become a self-sustaining organization, the organization faces both challenges and

opportunities. Sustainability is an urgent priority, requiring NDSA to reimagine its funding model and governance structure to ensure its long-term viability. This transition will determine not only the future of NDSA, but also the continued availability of its widely used resources and the strength of the community it supports.

NDSA's transition to a new host marks a pivotal moment in its evolution, reflecting both the growth of the organization and the changing landscape of digital preservation. While this shift presents challenges, it also creates opportunities to strengthen NDSA's governance, expand its impact, and build a more sustainable foundation for the future. By investing in leadership, fostering deeper engagement with its members, and refining its operational model, NDSA can continue to serve as a vital hub for collaboration, advocacy, and knowledge-sharing in the digital preservation community. Through this next phase, NDSA remains committed to ensuring the longevity and accessibility of digital information.

VI. SOFTWARE PRESERVATION NETWORK (SPN)

The Software Preservation Network (SPN) is a coordinated, distributed effort to ensure long term access to software through community engagement, infrastructure support, and knowledge generation. SPN creates a space in which organizations and individuals from cultural heritage, academia, government, and industry can build collaborative solutions for persistent access to software and software-dependent data.

EAASI (Emulation-as-a-Service Infrastructure) is open-source software, product-managed by Yale Library's Software Preservation and Emulation team, that facilitates interactive, controlled access to digital cultural heritage and research by making emulation easier.

Over the last seven years, SPN and EAASI have grown up together, collaborating on community cultivation, law and policy initiatives, and research on using EAASI to access software-dependent collections. In 2024, several factors motivated a major transition for SPN:

- SPN needed a differentiated value proposition, more capacity to achieve its ambitions, and increased revenue to fund a

full-time employee (a requirement introduced by its fiscal sponsor, Educopia Institute). SPN members needed shared technical infrastructure for providing access to software-dependent collections and putting SPN's outputs into practice.

- The EAASI team at Yale needed an organizational collaborator to sustain the EAASI community. EAASI was architected to be a multi-sided platform, to flourish through use by libraries, archives, and museums—a community like SPN.

With these factors in mind, Yale pitched a formal organizational collaboration in which Yale would continue to develop the EAASI software, SPN would become the exclusive entry point to the international EAASI Research Alliance of EAASI users, and SPN would adopt equity-centered fee tiers to expand its membership. The EAASI Research Alliance would offer SPN additional revenue for a full-time Program Manager and a differentiated value proposition to grow its capacity. SPN would offer EAASI a network of organizations who are invested in preserving access. SPN members approved the collaboration and implementation is underway.

Throughout this restructuring year, SPN and the EAASI team learned that you can only plan for so much and must stay true to the spirit of the community. Community calls moved from explorational conversations to essential business meetings in preparation for change. In that process, we paused a lot of what made our community special. SPN members craved a return to learning together what it means to do software preservation. Attending the organizational structure has to be in parallel with the needs of the communities, so while it's important to maintain our organizational integrity, we have to continue to experiment with our research and practice for our community to flourish.

We also witnessed the importance of collective action to achieve individual goals. EAASI can serve as common infrastructure for operationalizing SPN's outputs and advancing individual member organizations' local objectives. No single organization can preserve software alone; collective action is our competitive advantage as a field. Particularly in this time of geopolitical uncertainty, we hope SPN can be a powerful site of

the collective action that organizations will require to thrive.

VII. CONCLUSION

All five collaborations found one thing in common: precarity. As digital preservation continues to evolve, we must recognize that no single model fits all communities of practice. Instead, we operate as a network of independent efforts, each shaped by distinct institutional as well as national contexts, funding environments, and community priorities. These initiatives are driven by deep expertise, creativity, and commitment, but also face diverse and often complex challenges. Moving forward, our greatest opportunity lies in strengthening the connective tissue between these efforts: building trust across communities, fostering transparency, sharing resources and knowledge, and developing strategies for collective resilience. By collaborating more intentionally, we can better navigate the shifting landscape and amplify the impact of our work.

At the same time, many of us are doing the work of nonprofit management and software product management with no formal training or adequate institutional support. We are balancing sustainability, financial constraints, and accessibility while ensuring that our tools and programs continue to serve the needs of the community. This includes managing communication and transparency to members. Resource management and capacity building will be key to ensure we do not burn out, that we pass along institutional knowledge, and that we develop strategies to maintain momentum even as conditions shift.

The challenges we face are not just technological hurdles or resource limitations. Austerity measures, stemming from budget constraints, and a lack of leadership buy-in have created an environment where community-driven initiatives struggle to gain the support they need. Many of us came to this work as archivists, librarians, technologists, and researchers—not as nonprofit administrators. Yet increasingly, we find ourselves navigating the complexities of fiscal sponsorship models, fundraising strategies, legal compliance, and governance structures without formal training or institutional support. We've been thrust into roles requiring expertise in areas like budgeting, board

development, and organizational management—skills rarely included in our professional education. This mismatch between our training and the demands of sustaining community organizations creates both personal and structural strain, highlighting the urgent need for shared resources, mentorship, and professional development opportunities tailored to community-based digital preservation work. The lack of support for these activities actively hinders the sustainable growth of digital preservation and tools, making it even more critical for us to build cross-organizational collaborations.

This is a call to action. We cannot do this work alone. To truly strengthen digital preservation, we need broader commitment—from within our communities and from the institutions, funders, and sponsors that support us. We must:

- Invest in community infrastructure by recognizing community-based organizations as essential digital preservation infrastructure worthy of sustained funding, rather than project-based funding.
- Explore shared service models to reduce duplication and increase sustainability across similar organizations.
- Support capacity building in nonprofit governance, fundraising, and strategic planning to empower our leaders and volunteers with the skills they need to succeed.
- Develop equitable, accessible models that lower barriers to participation and recognize the value of all types of labor, including emotional, volunteer, and lived experience.
- Adopt mutual aid frameworks to share tools, documentation, training materials, and funding strategies across organizational boundaries.
- Center transparency and succession planning in our governance, to support smoother transitions and prevent knowledge loss.

To thrive, we must move beyond survival. Sustaining our organizations means sustaining our people: investing in their labor, acknowledging their contributions, and creating space for growth, innovation, and experimentation. Our strength lies in collective action. Through solidarity, shared vision,

and ongoing collaboration, we can ensure that our communities—and the digital legacies we protect—remain resilient in the face of change.

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